

Analyst Administrator
Date Wednesday, July 6, 2022 4:49 PM

Sample Name	Description	Quality Checks
CAS-147-6_1	Sample 007 By Administrator Date Wednesday, July 06 2022	The Quality Checks give rise to a Weak Bands warning for the sample.